

SIDE EFFECTS OF CHEMOTHERAPY FOR WOMEN**Madaminov Sodiq Madaminovich****To'lqinov Islomjon Ikromjon o'g'li**

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Annotation. Chemotherapy is one of the most common forms of cancer treatment. But chemotherapy does a lot more than get rid of cancer. Chemotherapy (often abbreviated to chemo and sometimes CTX or CTx) is a type of cancer treatment that uses one or more anti-cancer drugs (chemotherapeutic agents or alkylating agents) as part of a standardized chemotherapy regimen. Chemotherapy may be given with a curative intent (which almost always involves combinations of drugs) or it may aim to prolong life or to reduce symptoms (palliative chemotherapy). Chemotherapy is one of the major categories of the medical discipline specifically devoted to pharmacotherapy for cancer, which is called medical oncology[1,2,3].

Key words: chemotherapy, cancer, side effects, anemia, fetus, birth defects, cardiomyopathy, neutropenia.

INTRODUCTION

The term chemotherapy has come to connote non-specific usage of intracellular poisons to inhibit mitosis (cell division) or induce DNA damage, which is why inhibition of DNA repair can augment chemotherapy. The connotation of the word chemotherapy excludes more selective agents that block extracellular signals (signal transduction). The development of therapies with specific molecular or genetic targets, which inhibit growth-promoting signals from classic endocrine hormones (primarily estrogens for breast cancer and androgens for prostate cancer) are now called hormonal therapies[4,5,6,7]. By contrast, other inhibitions of growth-signals like those associated with receptor tyrosine kinases are referred to as targeted therapy.

Importantly, the use of drugs (whether chemotherapy, hormonal therapy or targeted therapy) constitutes systemic therapy for cancer in that they are introduced into the blood stream and are therefore in principle able to address cancer at any anatomic location in the body. Systemic therapy is often used in conjunction with other modalities that constitute local therapy (i.e., treatments whose efficacy is confined to the anatomic area where they are applied) for cancer such as radiation therapy[8,9], surgery or hyperthermia therapy.

Traditional chemotherapeutic agents are cytotoxic by means of interfering with cell division (mitosis) but cancer cells vary widely in their

susceptibility to these agents. To a large extent, chemotherapy can be thought of as a way to damage or stress cells, which may then lead to cell death if apoptosis is initiated[10,11]. Many of the side effects of chemotherapy can be traced to damage to normal cells that divide rapidly and are thus sensitive to anti-mitotic drugs: cells in the bone marrow, digestive tract and hair follicles. This results in the most common side-effects of chemotherapy: myelosuppression (decreased production of blood cells, hence that also immunosuppression), mucositis (inflammation of the lining of the digestive tract), and alopecia (hair loss). Because of the effect on immune cells (especially lymphocytes), chemotherapy drugs often find use in a host of diseases that result from harmful overactivity of the immune system against self (so-called autoimmunity). These include rheumatoid arthritis [12,13,14,15], systemic lupus erythematosus, multiple sclerosis, vasculitis and many others. Rather than men, women more suffer from chemotherapy. In addition, Pregnant women are in higher risk

The purpose of the study. In this study, we are learning how have side effects of chemotherapy for women

Chemotherapy is one of the most common forms of cancer treatment. But chemotherapy does a lot more than get rid of cancer. While chemotherapy drugs are powerful enough to kill rapidly growing cancer cells, they can also harm healthy cells. This may cause a variety of side effects. The severity of these side effects depends on: your overall health the stage of your cancer the type and amount of chemotherapy you receive. Many side effects clear up shortly after treatment ends, but some may continue for months, years, or may never go away. It is important to discuss any side effects you're experiencing with your doctor. In some cases, depending on the reactions your body is having, your doctor may need to adjust the type or dose of chemotherapy. Chemotherapy drugs can affect any body system, but may especially hair follicles bone marrow mouth reproductive system. It's worth understanding how these cancer drugs can affect your major body systems: Routine blood count monitoring is a crucial part of chemotherapy. The drugs can cause a loss of healthy red blood cells, resulting in anemia.

Symptoms of anemia may include: fatigue, lightheadedness, pale skin shortness of breath, chest pain, rapid heart rate. Chemo can also cause neutropenia, a condition where you have a low white blood cell count. White blood cells play an important role in the immune system and help fight infections[16]. It's important to take precautions to avoid exposure to viruses

and bacteria if you're receiving chemo. A low platelet count, called thrombocytopenia, can also occur with chemotherapy. Cells called platelets help blood clot. Low numbers of them mean you're likely to bruise and bleed easily. Symptoms may include: small red dots on your skin called petechiae heavier than normal menstruation . Some chemo drugs may also damage the heart, potentially leading to cardiomyopathy, or heart muscle disease. It can also disturb your heart rhythm, a condition called arrhythmia. These conditions can affect your heart's ability to pump blood effectively. These problems are less likely to occur if your heart is strong and healthy when you start chemotherapy. Chemotherapy drugs alter hormones in both men and women. In women, hot flashes, irregular periods, sudden onset of menopause , dryness of vaginal tissues infertility. In men, some chemo drugs can harm sperm or lower sperm count. Like women, men can have temporary or permanent infertility from chemo[16,17]. Doctors advise against getting pregnant during chemotherapy treatment. Chemotherapy drugs can damage sperm and can also harm the fetus if given during pregnancy, possibly leading to birth defects. If you are already pregnant when you receive a cancer diagnosis, you still have options. You and your doctor will discuss the next best steps. Treatment may involve surgery rather than chemo, or different timing of treatment. While symptoms like fatigue and anxiety may interfere with sex drive in both men and women, many people on chemotherapy are still able to have active sex lives. Chemotherapy may be given with a curative intent or it may aim to prolong life or to palliate symptoms[17,18].

- Induction chemotherapy is the first line treatment of cancer with a chemotherapeutic drug. This type of chemotherapy is used for curative intent.

- Combined modality chemotherapy is the use of drugs with other cancer treatments, such as surgery, radiation therapy, or hyperthermia therapy[19].

- Consolidation chemotherapy is given after remission in order to prolong the overall disease-free time and improve overall survival. The drug that is administered is the same as the drug that achieved remission.

- Intensification chemotherapy is identical to consolidation chemotherapy but a different drug than the induction chemotherapy is used.

- Combination chemotherapy involves treating a person with a number of different drugs simultaneously. The drugs differ in their mechanism and side-effects. The biggest advantage is minimising the chances

of resistance developing to any one agent. Also, the drugs can often be used at lower doses, reducing toxicity.

- Neoadjuvant chemotherapy is given prior to a local treatment such as surgery, and is designed to shrink the primary tumor. It is also given for cancers with a high risk of micrometastatic disease.

- Adjuvant chemotherapy is given after a local treatment (radiotherapy or surgery). It can be used when there is little evidence of cancer present, but there is risk of recurrence. It is also useful in killing any cancerous cells that have spread to other parts of the body. These micrometastases can be treated with adjuvant chemotherapy and can reduce relapse rates caused by these disseminated cells.

- Maintenance chemotherapy is a repeated low-dose treatment to prolong remission.

- Salvage chemotherapy or palliative chemotherapy is given without curative intent, but simply to decrease tumor load and increase life expectancy. For these regimens, in general, a better toxicity profile is expected.

CONCLUSIONS.

All chemotherapy regimens require that the recipient be capable of undergoing the treatment. Performance status is often used as a measure to determine whether a person can receive chemotherapy, or whether dose reduction is required[20,21]. Because only a fraction of the cells in a tumor die with each treatment (fractional kill), repeated doses must be administered to continue to reduce the size of the tumor. Current chemotherapy regimens apply drug treatment in cycles, with the frequency and duration of treatments limited by toxicity.

Chemo is more toxic for women. Chemotherapy drugs alter hormones in both men and women. In women, hot flashes, irregular periods, sudden onset of menopause, dryness of vaginal tissues, infertility.

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